

The role of school and family factors in moderating cyberbullying victimization consequences: A protocol for a meta-analysis

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Abstract

Previous literature (Sampasa-Kanyinga et al., 2020; Wright & Wachs, 2023) indicates family and school factors as relevant dimensions in explaining the association of bullying and cyberbullying with internalizing problems. These factors may moderate the associations of bullying and cyberbullying with internalizing problems, but this hypothesis has never been investigated in meta-analysis. Due to this paucity, this meta-analysis will be conducted to investigate the roles of family- and school-related risk and protective factors in the development of internalizing problems in children and adolescents in relation to cyberbullying and traditional bullying victimization.

We will conduct this meta-analysis as an extension of Barlett et al. (2023). For reporting the study results, PRISMA guidelines will be employed. The studies on the consequences of cyberbullying victimization that have been included in Barlett et al. (2023) will be used. Additionally, a new database search will be conducted to identify studies published after the end of the database search in Barlett et al. (2023). We will conduct rigorous searching and data extraction procedures using the same databases and search strings. We will screen these articles to understand the impact of cyberbullying victimization on the internalizing issues of children and adolescents, aged up to 18, while taking into account the role of risk and protective factors related to family and school. Two independent peer-reviewed processes will be carried out for the title, abstract, and full text review. In order to evaluate the effect size of the cyberbullying victimization on the internalizing problems by considering the role of the traditional bullying, partial correlation will be used. Then the interaction of the school and family factors with the cyberbullying victimization and

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internalizing problems will be evaluated.

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Keywords: cyberbullying, victimization, school factors, family factors, internalizing problems.

Introduction

Background and Rationale

Internet-based technology has become one of the most vital sources of communication for people, in recent decades. The worldwide prevalence of use of the internet among individuals aged 15 to 24 is reached out 75% in 2022 (International Telecommunication Union, 2022). Although the internet eases being in touch with family members and friends, the possibility of shopping online, and the accessibility of knowledge, it also brings new problems that have the potential to harm individuals, including but not limited to cyberharrassment, cyberbullying, and cyberbullying victimization (Smith, 2018).

Cyberbullying has been defined as a deliberate and repetitive act of causing harm to someone on an online platform, particularly targeting individuals who are unable to protect themselves (Barlett et al., 2023). Even though cyberbullying and traditional bullying share communal characteristics, they also have unique qualities. For example, the possible anonymity of the perpetrator, at least to some degree, the conceptualization of the power differences between the victim and the perpetrator, and the definition of the repetition of the act are different for traditional bullying and cyberbullying (Barlett et al., 2023; Camerini et al., 2020). Also, the other potential risk is being spread out in the online environment without knowing who has witnessed the cyberbullying instances (Gradinger et al., 2012).

Victimization is recognized as one of the primary risk factors for the adjustment problems of individuals. The possibility of the development of internalizing problems such as loneliness or depression (Gini et al., 2017) in relation to negative self-evaluation as a result of peer victimization (Lopez & DuBois, 2005) increases. Regarding the stability of victimization, bullying instances, by definition, are obtained as stable victimization behaviors, and all around the world, cyberbullying is a prevalent and deleterious problem for the wellbeing of individuals (Zych et al., 2015). Previous studies showed that stability amplifies the development of maladjustment problems such as anxiety, depression, and low self-esteem (Rueger et al., 2011). Moreover, the challenges associated with identifying internalizing problems in contrast to externalizing problems might lead to the exacerbation of these symptoms and have long-lasting effects on individuals (Brown et al., 2007). Childhood victimization or bullying may convey to the development of internalizing problems (Guzman-Holst & Bowes, 2021). Research has demonstrated a significant association of stable victimization and cyberbullying with internalizing problems (Gini et al., 2017).

Young people are a risky group for cyberbullying incidences because of their extended knowledge of using internet technology but limited understanding of the

detrimental outcomes and tendency to engage in risk-taking behaviors (Smith, 2018). In middle adolescence, around the age of 14, cybervictimization has the highest percentage, and it decreases around late adolescence (Sumter et al., 2012). Additionally, studies that focused on the relationship between children and cyberbullying revealed that almost one in every five students in primary school experienced cybervictimization (Camerini et al., 2020). Considering the prevalence of experiencing risky events and the increase number of cyberbullying victimization adolescence and childhood turns out to be a critical age group to examine cybervictimization.

The contribution of cyberbullying victimization to the wellbeing and mental health of individuals can be dependent on the other factors that moderate this relationship (Barlett et al., 2023). In alignment with the ecological systems theories of Bronfenbrenner (1989), several studies have also started to reveal how the micro-level school and familial factors and the meso-level interaction of family and school environment differentiate the association of cyberbullying victimization with internalizing problems. A study conducted with primary, middle, and high school students shows that parental support prevents the development of depression in the aftermath of cyberbullying victimization for all age groups, and peer support buffers the development of depression for middle school students (Wright & Wachs, 2023). It is also found that negative parent-child relationships amplified the development of psychological distress following the cybervictimization of adolescents (Sampasa-Kanyinga et al., 2020).

Even though the consequences of cyberbullying victimization have been extensively studied and the factors that moderate this relationship have been investigated, the literature still has conceptual and methodological gaps. Due to the differences in variables, measures, and samples, the studies can provide inconsistent results. Therefore, as suggested by Farrington et al. (2023), cyberbullying should be studied from a systematic and comprehensive perspective. In addition to that, using only simple bivariate correlation to estimate the effect size of cyberbullying victimization on internalizing problems may exaggerate the effect sizes (Polanin et al., 2021). Consequently, although the outcomes of cyberbullying victimization were studied in various meta-analyses (Farrington et al., 2023; Fisher et al., 2016; Li et al., 2022), how and to what degree school- and family-related factors moderate the consequences of cyberbullying victimization remains to be investigated.

Previous meta-analyses

Two meta-analyses were carried out to investigate the distinct contribution of cyberbullying in comparison to traditional bullying. Gini et al. (2017) revealed that

cyberbullying victimization and traditional bullying victimization were uniquely related to internalizing problems of adolescents. Furthermore, the recent study by Barlett et al. (2023) extended the scope of Gini et al. (2017) by including all ages from childhood to adulthood, and focused on the relation of cyberbullying victimization to the mental health and well-being of individuals. Their study supported the findings of the previous study and demonstrated that, controlling for traditional bullying victimization, cyberbullying victimization was significantly associated with most of the wellbeing and mental health outcomes, including anxiety, depression, loneliness, and self-esteem of individuals.

Objective and review questions

Up until now, no research has looked into how familial- and school-related factors moderate the link between the association of cyberbullying victimization and internalizing problems. Considering the factors that moderate the association of bullying with developmental outcomes (Espelage et al., 2012; McGuire & Norman, 2018), we aim to disentangle the role of family- and school-related factors in the association of cyberbullying victimization with internalizing problems. For the present study, we chose to focus on the association of cyberbullying victimization with internalizing problems for risky age groups, including children and adolescents.

This study will consider family-related factors that directly influence family dynamics, including the quality of parent-child relationships, communication patterns with parents, the socioeconomic status of the family, sibling relationships, and adverse childhood experiences. We will also investigate indirect factors like the quality of spousal relationships, parental education, and the work-family conflict parents experience. Furthermore, the safety of the school environment, the quality of peer relationships, the sense of belongingness to school, and the level of support provided by teachers will be investigated as school-related risks and protective factors.

The primary research question for this study is: Is the association of cyberbullying victimization with internalizing problems moderated by family- and school-related risks and protective factors controlling for traditional bullying? We are also interested in investigating the relative role of family or school factors in explaining the association of cyberbullying victimization with internalizing problems. However, the possibility of answering this research question depends on the number of existing primary studies that involve both family- and school-related risk and protective factors.

As far as we know, this will be the first meta-analysis to examine the role of family- and school-related factors as moderators in the association of cyberbullying victimization

with the internalizing problems of children and adolescents. The results of this study will provide information on how and to what degree the family and school factors moderate the association of cyberbullying victimization with the internalizing problems of children and adolescents. These findings may contribute to the development of effective intervention programs by addressing the social ecology of children and adolescents.

Methods

Meta-analysis is the most appropriate strategy for this study since it can produce comprehensive information from the existing literature and provide tools for intervention studies (Page et al., 2021). The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA; Page et al., 2021) will be employed to present the systematic procedures and to illustrate the study's findings. We will register this protocol using the Open Science Framework (<https://osf.io/6hak7/>).

Eligibility criteria

The study of Barlett et al. (2023) served as a baseline for this paper's eligibility criteria, albeit with some modifications. The eligibility criteria are also open to being adjusted during the screening and data extraction processes.

Population

Although Barlett et al. (2023) did not provide specific criteria for their sample, in this study we limited our sample to children and adolescents. We include studies conducted with individuals under the age of 18. The inclusion and exclusion criteria of the study are presented in Table 1.

Cyberbullying and traditional bullying

This meta-analysis investigates the distinct role of cyberbullying victimization in the internalizing problems of children and adolescents. Similar to the research conducted by Barlett et al. (2023), peer-reviewed studies in which cyberbullying victimization has been defined and investigated and traditional bullying victimization is controlled, are included in the study.

Moderators

In order to investigate the role of family- and school-related factors within the association of cyberbullying victimization with the internalizing problems of children and adolescents, in addition to the criteria of Barlett et al. (2023), studies including at least one familial- or school -related risk or protective factors are included.

Internalizing problems

In the present study, we operationalize internalizing problems based on the conceptualization of Forns et al. (2018) and Guzman-Holst and Bowes (2021). Internalizing symptoms refer to "inner-directed and distress-generating" problems (Forns et al., 2018), which include the presence of symptoms related to anxiety and depression, physical complaints associated with these symptoms, and a tendency to withdraw socially and emotionally (Merrell, 2018). In addition, we will take into account the hidden signs of

internalizing issues, such as feelings of isolation and the tendency to withdraw from social interactions, experiencing sadness or having a diminished sense of self-worth, difficulties with focus and attention, as well as sleep disturbances (not classified as disorders) (Guzman-Holst and Bowes, 2021). Furthermore, the symptoms of major depression, such as suicidal ideations and thoughts (Guzman-Holst and Bowes, 2021), will be examined as outcome variables in this study.

Criterion for study selection

Quantitative studies with longitudinal, cross-sectional, cross-sequential, and experimental/quasi experimental designs are included. This study will not have a specific starting date. Studies in Barlett et al. (2023) and the current literature from January 2022, the end of Barlett et al.'s (2023) database search, until the beginning of June 2024 are included. We did not provide any geographical restrictions for the studies. In order to screen articles by independent reviewers, and compute the inter-rater reliability, the language of the articles will be limited to English, which is the common language of the authors.

Table 1. Eligibility criteria for the study selection

	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Population	Children and adolescents under the age of 18. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adolescents at the age of 18 are included. - If a study includes a mixed group of adolescents, including late adolescents (above the age of 18), statistical measures of interest will be computed based on the children and adolescents under the age of 18. If it represents at least more than 50% of the total sample, the study will be included. - Longitudinal studies from childhood to late adolescents in which the analyses were conducted before the age of 18. 	Individuals over the age of 18. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If a study includes a mixed group of adolescents, including late adolescents (above the age of 18), statistical measures of interest will be computed based on the children and adolescents under the age of 18. If it represents less than 50% of the total sample, the study will be excluded. - Longitudinal studies from childhood to late adolescents in which the analyses were conducted after 18.
Victimization type	Studies examine both cyberbullying victimization and traditional bullying victimization. Bullying and cyberbullying victimization should be measured by self-report	Studies that do not suit the operational definition of cyberbullying and traditional bullying victimization. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Studies measured

Type of moderator	<p>with at least on quantitative item.</p> <p>The study should include at least one familial- or school-related risk or protective factor that measured at least one quantitative item.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Studies which don't have moderators but meet all other criteria will be included to compute the mean effect sizes of the unique contribution on the cyberbullying victimization. 	<p>cyberbullying and traditional bullying based on reports of others or based on narratives.</p> <p>Studies measure moderator with a qualitative measure will be excluded.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Studies which don't have moderators even though they meet all other criteria will be excluded to compute the role of the family and school related factors in the association of cyberbullying victimization with internalizing problems.
Internalizing problems	<p>Studies include at least one of the internalizing problems, such as depression, anxiety, social anxiety, or loneliness, measured at least one quantitative item are included.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cross-sectional studies that investigate the association of internalizing problems with cyberbullying victimization will also be included. 	<p>Internalizing problems, which are not operationalized in the definition and includes factors that can be only associated with internalizing problems such as self-esteem.</p>
Study type	<p>Peer-reviewed quantitative articles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quantitative part of the mixed-methods studies which meet all other criteria for the measure of the focused variables. 	<p>Mixed-method studies with qualitative measures for bullying, cyberbullying, internalizing problems, and moderator variables.</p>
Context	<p>Studies conducted all around the world.</p>	<p>No restriction.</p>
Language	<p>English</p>	<p>Studies published in another language than English.</p>
Type of analysis	<p>Correlation matrix to analyze the partial correlation among variables</p>	

Search strategy

The screening process will consist of two distinct phases, and two independent reviewers will participate in all phases. First, the articles used in Barlett et al. (2023) will be screened based on the eligibility criteria. Secondly, we will systematically search the databases used in Barlett et al. (2023) after their termination date to incorporate the most

recent studies.

Databases and search terms: In order to extend the literature review to include the most recent publications, the same search strategy and terms as in Barlett et al. (2023), will be used with slight modifications. The same electronic sources as in Barlett et al. (2023): Academic Search Complete, Business Source Complete, Communication & Mass Media Complete, Criminal Justice Abstracts, Education Research Complete, Family Studies Abstracts, HealthSource: Nursing/Academic Edition, Human Resources Abstracts, MEDLINE, PsycARTICLES, PsycINFO, SocINDEX, and Social Sciences Full Text will be employed.

As in the Barlett et al. (2023) meta-analysis, several search terms will be used, to include different terminologies correspond to cyberbullying victimization. Sexual online harassment and stalking will be kept out of the discussion to limit the scope of the study. Sex* and stalk* terms will therefore be restricted. In order to include just the internalizing problems as outcome variables, the search terms of Barlett et al. (2023) have been slightly modified and outcome variables that are not related to internalizing problems will be excluded from the search terms. Furthermore, to restrict the sample of the study to children and adolescents, new search terms for the sample will be included. The search terms of the present study are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Search terms for the main variables

Concepts	Search terms
Cyberbullying victimization	(cyber* OR Internet OR net OR web* OR online OR chat OR electronic) AND (harass* OR bully* OR victim* OR perpetr*)
Internalizing problems	(anxi* OR depress* OR lonel* OR somatic* OR symptom* OR health OR anonym* OR attit*)
Children and adolescents	(child OR children OR youth OR young* OR toddler* OR adolescen* OR teen* OR pre-teen* OR minor* OR minors OR schoolchild* OR kid* OR boy* OR girl* OR student* OR pupil* OR pre adoles* OR preadoles*)

Study selection

Based on the abovementioned inclusion and exclusion criteria:

- 1) In order to ensure the inter-rater reliability, the first screening, second screening, and the data extraction will be completed by two independent researchers. A pilot screening in which the 10% of articles are randomly chosen will be conducted with

another independent reviewer to confirm the process. The disagreements for the articles by independent reviewers will be discussed and dissolved by the research group.

- 2) In the first screening, studies included in Barlett et al. (2023) and the articles found in the database searching will be screened by their title and abstract. Articles will be screened by two independent reviewer until a substantial level of inter-rater reliability is ensured.
- 3) Following the first screening procedure, two researchers will independently read the full text of the retrieved articles and in align with the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and extract the information.
- 4) The research team will contact the authors of the selected primary studies for missing summary statistics. The research team will send one reminder to authors in two weeks, and after a waiting period of two weeks, the call for the missing information will be terminated.
- 5) Rayyan (Ouzzani et al., 2016) will be used to conduct the screening process of the articles from the new database search and the second screening of all articles. The results of the screening procedure will be reported based on the PRISMA flowchart (Polanin et al., 2021).

Data extraction

Information about studies will be extracted based on the prepared codebook. In order to validate and calibrate the codebook, a pilot study comprising 10% randomly chosen articles will be conducted by the research group. Following the pilot study, the research team will meet and discuss the validity of the codebook and the consistency of the extraction results. The necessary adjustments will be implemented in the codebook. Following the adjustment of the codebook, two independent researchers will work on the extraction of the information. For longitudinal studies, baseline wave and pretest/control group data of the experimental studies will be considered. The same data call procedure to contact the authors for any missing information. "NP, Not Reported" will be coded if the writers are unable to obtain the information. The codebook includes information about five levels of information: study level, sample characteristics, predictor level (bullying and cyberbullying), outcome level (internalizing problems), and moderator level (family and school-related protective and risk factors). The example of the codebook is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. The codebook for the data extraction

Study level information										
Article ID	Rater	Citation (APA 7)	Authors	Title	Year	Country	Design	Data of the study is public (1) private (0)	The study is funded (1) no (0)	Dataset name
	Sample characteristics				Bullying and cyberbullying					
Moderator variable included (1) not (0)	Number of participants	Gender (female %)	Mean age of the sample	Sampling design Convenience (0) Random (1)	Definition of TV and CV provided (1) not (0)	TV is controlled (1) not (0)	Name and citation of the measure CV	Name and citation of the measure TV	Rating scale of CV	Rating scale of TV
									Internalizing problems	
Number of CV items	Number of TV items	Reliability of CV	Reliability of TV	Mean of CV	SD of CV	Mean of TV	SD of TV	Correlation of CV with TV (r coefficient)	Type of internalizing problems	Type of data collection
									Family and school related protective and risk factors	
Name and citation of internalizing measure	Rating scale	Number of internalizing problem items	Reliability of the internalizing problems	Mean of internalizing problems	SD of internalizing problems	Correlation with CV	Correlation with TV	Type of family protective factors	Type of data collection FPF	Name and citation of the FPF measure
Rating scale of FPF	Number of FPF items	Reliability of the FPF	Mean of FPF	SD of FPF	Correlation of FPF with CV	Correlation of FPF with TV	Correlation of FPF with internalizing problems	Type of family risk factors	Type of data collection FRF	Name and citation of the FRF measure
Rating scale	Number of	Reliability	Mean of FRF	SD of FRF	Correlation of	Correlation of	Correlation of	Type of	Type of data	Name and

of FRF	FRF items	of the FRF			FRF with CV	FRF with TV	FRF with internalizing problems	school protective factors	collection SPF	citation of the SPF measure
Rating scale of SPF	Number of SPF items	Reliability of the SPF	Mean of SPF	SD of SPF	Correlation of SPF with CV	Correlation of SPF with TV	Correlation of SPF with internalizing problems	Type of school risk factors	Type of data collection SRF	Name and citation of the SRF measure
Rating scale of SRF	Number of SRF items	Reliability of the SRF	Mean of SRF	SD of SRF	Correlation of SRF with CV	Correlation of SRF with TV	Correlation of SRF with internalizing problems			

Analysis Methods

In this study, we are going to estimate effect sizes in two phases:

a) In order to estimate the effect size of cyberbullying victimization on internalizing problems controlling for the traditional bullying, we will compute standardized slopes to obtain the semi-partial correlations.

b) If we can obtain an adequate number of studies for moderation analysis, in the second phase, we will disentangle the role of family and school related risks and protective factors in the association of cyberbullying victimization with internalizing problems. For this analysis, we will group moderators into four categories: family related risk factors, family-related protective factors, school-related risk factors, and school related protective factors.

Similar to Barlett et al.'s (2023) methodological approach, this study will utilize R version 4.3.3 (R Core Team, 2024) to evaluate effect sizes, as well as the relation of family and school-related factors across studies.

We anticipate possible multiple effect sizes from the same study will lead to a dependency among the effect sizes. Therefore, in order to aggregate the multiple effect sizes from the same study, similar to Barlett et al (2023), we will carry out a random effects model. We will employ Q-test and I2 statistics in order to examine the heterogeneity within the effect sizes.

Missing value

In order to handle missing values, we are going to use “infer, initiate, impute,” similar to Polanin et al. (2021). First, we will try to infer missing data from the presented information. For example, if the age of the participants wasn't presented in the study but the grade, then we will infer age from the grade of the participants. However, if we don't have reference information for inference, as we mentioned above, we are going to contact the author for the missing information. If we still have missing information, we will impute the missing information (Polanin et al., 2021).

Assessment of risk of bias in included studies

The risk of bias in the included studies will be evaluated based on the Cochrane Methods' bias assessment tool (De La Rue et al., 2013). Similar to De La Rue et al. (2013), studies will not be excluded based on the results of the bias assessment tool, and the information will be used to evaluate the heterogeneity in the meta-analysis.

In order to estimate the publication biases, a funnel plot will be implemented. Sensitivity analyses will be carried out in R software (R Core Team, 2024) in two phases: first, the outlier studies will be excluded separately. The analysis will be repeated after

including the outlier studies. The results will be assessed based on the confidence interval (%95) (Barlett et al., 2023).

Ethics and dissemination

For the present study, we will use published, peer-reviewed articles as a source of information. Therefore, this study does not require ethical approval. Besides the experts in the research group, a librarian will be consulted for the revision of search terms, database search, and article retrieval. The present study will be published in scientific peer-reviewed journals as a product of the study. Additionally, as a dissemination activity, the research group will participate in scientific conferences.

Conclusion

The present study will investigate the role of family and school-related risk and protective factors in the association of cyberbullying victimization with internalizing problems. This study will shed light on the uninflated effect of internalizing problems as a victim of cyberbullying and offer suggestions for a novel meta-analysis methodology. The results of this will also be beneficial for people who are in direct relationships with children and adolescents, such as parents and teachers. Also, people who are not in direct relationships but have policy-making roles on behalf of children and adolescents will utilize the present study. These findings will shed light on a world where adversities can occur, but where families and educational settings can still play a protective role in keeping children and adolescents safe and healthy.

Roles and Responsibilities

The roles and responsibilities of the researchers are specified considering their expertise and responsibilities in MSCA – Participate project.

- Content: Ebru Ozbek, Simona Caravita, Ida Risanger Sjursø
- Systematic review and data extraction: Ebru Ozbek, Ida Risanger Sjursø
- Statistical analysis: Ebru Ozbek, Takuya Yanagida, Simona Caravita
- Information retrieval: Ebru Ozbek, Simona Caravita

Ebru Ozbek will be responsible for the retrieval of the articles, coding and screening of the study information, and writing literature and reporting. She will carry out the analyses under the supervision of Takuya Yanagida and Simona Caravita. The responsibilities of Ida Risanger Sjursø include providing and reporting the literature on the consequences of cyberbullying victimization, screening procedures, and synthesizing the article. Aside from consulting on cyberbullying victimization, Simona Caravita is responsible for supervising the coding and screening procedures and synthesizing the findings. Takuya Yanagida is the primary consultant on methodological issues and synthesizing the findings of the meta-regression analysis.

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